

ROLE OF POLICE IN PREVENTION OF ENVIRONMENTAL CRIME: INDAs PERSPECTIVE AND LEGAL FRAMEWORK.

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Abstract:

The primary duty of Police to prevent crime and protects life and property through the enforcement of laws and regulations. For the protection of rights of the citizens the criminal Justice System has been constituted assigning important responsibility to the Police. Police have an indispensable role in administration of criminal justice on environmental matters through detecting crimes, inspecting and investigating violation, protecting business and tourist and community policing. Thus, the aim of this paper is to analyze the concept of Environmental Crime as describe under various international conventions. Further, it's also aim to analyze the present constitutional and Panel provisions in India for prevention of Environmental Crime and to identify the police services operating environmental law in India. The role that Police Administration play in the implementation of environmental laws and regulations be need of analysis and understanding if better enforcement policies are to be developed. Thus, this article will, emphasis on analyze the laws related to environmental crime and the role of police in prevention of Environmental Crime.

Key words: *environmental, crime, police, prevention*

Introduction

Environmental crime covers the complete range of activities that breach environmental legislation and cause significant harm or risk to the environment, human health or both. It is an illegal act which directly harms the environment. These illegal activities involve the environment, wildlife, biodiversity and natural resources. Environmental crimes are widely recognized as among some of the most profitable forms transnational criminal activity. According to the INTERPOL-UNEP report 2016, illegal activities that involve the environment, biodiversity or natural resources are often lucrative and involve comparatively low risks for criminals. A recent study by UN Environment title “the state of knowledge of crimes that have serious impacts on the Environment”, lists five of the most prevalent environmental crime areas globally. They are illegal wildlife trade, illegal logging, illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing, the pollution crime, and illegal mining. Offences like the illegal emission or discharge of substances into air, water or soil, illegal trade in wildlife and illegal shipment and dumping of waste can have devastating effects on the environment and human but often remain invisible. Environmental crime often affects society as a whole rather than individuals. It rarely involves victims informing police or courts of the committed crime.

That is why environmental crime is underestimated phenomenon. Thus, environmental crime is growing concern causing significant damage to human health and the economy. According to Interpol and United Nations Environmental Programme, environmental crime is the fourth largest criminal activity in the world after drug trafficking, human trafficking and counterfeiting, growing at a rate between 5%-7% per year, two or three times the pace of global economic growth.

Thus, the effective enforcement of Environmental laws is indispensable to any protection regimes that are design to protect environmental crime. In early days of environmental legislation, violations carried largely insignificant civil fines and penalties. Initial environmental laws and regulations had no deterrent effect on corporations, individuals or governments to comply with environmental laws. In many cases, particularly corporations found it most cost effective to continue to pollute more than the law allowed and simply pay any associate fine. As a result of weak environmental legislation and continued adverse public opinion regarding the management of the environment, many governments established various environmental enforcement regimes that dramatically increased the legal powers of environmental investigators. The inclusion of criminal sanctions, significance increase in fines coupled with possible imprisonment of corporate officers change the face of environmental law enforcement. Many environmental agencies play a vital role in reducing environmental damage and protecting the environment through environmental laws and regulations. These agencies operate at varying levels from International, National, State to local level. Various enforcement methods are employed by these agencies working at one level. Similarly, International Criminal Police Organization work on environmental crimes is supported by INTERPOL's Environmental Crime Working party, known as the Environmental Compliance and Enforcement Committee and its four specialized crime working groups on wildlife, forestry, fisheries and pollution crime. Furthermore, in India the Green Police is the main enforcement and deterrence arm of the Ministry of Environmental Protection. The 2011 Enforcement Protection Law (Powers of Inspection and Protection) gives them the power to open cases, manage criminal investigations, impose fine and sanction etc. Green Police inspectors are involved with both monitoring and enforcing Environmental laws, regulations and decrees. Green Police enforce environmental laws on three levels: National, Regional and Local. Thus, police have an important role in the administration of criminal justice on environmental crime.

Objective of the Study

Following are the objectives of the present study

1. To analyze the concept of Environmental Crime as described under various international conventions on the protection of Environment.
2. To analyze the present constitutional and penal framework in India for prevention of Environmental Crime.
3. To analyze the role of police in prevention of Environmental Crime in India.

Research Methodology

The methodology followed for the purpose of the study is doctrinal in nature. In order to undertake the present study, the secondary sources of data have been used, which includes books, journals, periodicals, statutes, newspapers etc.

International Campaign for the prevention of Environmental Crime

The Convention on the Protection of Environment through Criminal Law (Strasbourg, November 4, 1998) is the first international Convention to criminalize acts causing or likely to cause environmental damage and it is very important event in the development of Environmental Criminal Law. With respect to criminal law the Convention typifies intentional and negligent offences. The sanction available shall include imprisonment, corporative liability and pecuniary sanction and may include reinstatement of the environment. Likewise the International bodies such as G8, INTERPOL, European Union, UNEP, United Nations Interregional Crime and Justice Research Institute have recognized the various number of Environmental Crime.

The fight against transboundary wildlife crime received a boost at G8 Summit held from 17 to 18 June 2013 Laugh Erne.G8 Leaders recognized the need of tackle criminal trafficking and to strengthen border security, including in relation to illegal trafficking of wildlife noting the links to governance and the rule of law sources of funding for tourists. Further, the International Criminal Police Organization commonly known as INTERPOL is an international organization that facilitates worldwide police co-operation and crime control. INTERPOL have four global enforcement team (fisheries, Forestry, pollution and Wildlife) which help dismantle and criminal networks behind environmental crime by providing law enforcement agencies with the tools and expertise they need to protect the environment from being exploited by criminals. Again, on 15 December 2021, the European Union (EU) Commission adopted a proposal for a new EU directive aimed at tightening compliance with EU environmental laws through the introduction of new criminal offences, increased sanctions and better enforcement. Again, the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) is responsible for coordinating responses to environmental issues within the United Nations system. The EU Parliament have adopted a resolution on European Union Action plan against wildlife Trafficking. The resolution specifically welcomes UN environment expert's process to examine and document the current status of knowledge of crimes that have serious impact on the environment. This process notes that the legal boundaries between different types of environmental crimes are sometimes unclear, which can reduce opportunities for effective prosecution and punishment. Further, the United Nation Interregional crime and justice Research Institute is one of the five United Nations Research and training institute. The institute was found in 1968 to assist the international community in formulating and implementing improved policies in the field of crime prevention and criminal justice. Since 1991, UNICRI has contributed to combating crimes against the environment and related emerging threats through applied research, awareness and capacity building initiatives. UNICRI has built a strong International Network of exports and practitioners from major International Organization, law enforcement agencies, NGOs and academic entities active in the field. The Commission on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice is the principal

policymaking body of crime prevention and criminal justice. Recently, during the commission meeting held from 14 to 16 2022, national practitioners and policymakers, UN entities, other intergovernmental and international organizations, and civil society experts exchanged good practices and lessons learned in preventing and combating these crimes and strengthening international cooperation. The Commission also highlighted those crimes that affect the environment are among the most profitable crimes with manifold negative impacts. Addressing such crimes is an integral element to achieving Agenda 2030 and addressing the biodiversity and climate crisis.

Constitutional and Panel Provisions in India

In our Constitution, it is vividly expressed that Directive Principles of State Policy are bent towards the idea of Welfare State and healthy environment is said to be an essential ingredient for welfare state. Article 47 states that the state shall regard the raising the level of nutrition and the standard of living of its people and also the improvement of public health which includes the protection and improvement of environment as a part of its primary duties. However, it also has the concern for the preservation of natural resources which is evident from the constitutional provisions enshrined in Art.48A and 51A(g). These two provisions make it obligatory on the part of the state as well as citizens to protect the environment. Environmental aspect has been read and interpreted by the Indian courts as a natural corollary to various other provisions of the Constitution. Soon after introduction of this vital fundamental duty of the citizen, Indian Supreme Court recognized the right to clean and wholesome environment as very important landmark in the development of Environmental Jurisprudence in India. The Supreme Court of India has liberally interpreted Art. 21 in order to maintain a balance between development and environment protection. The Supreme Court of India in plethora of decision also recognized the right to livelihood of those people who has been displaced in the wake of industrial development causing massive depletion of forests, wildlife and natural resources.

Chapter XIV of the Indian Penal Code, 1860 deals with offences affecting the “public safety, health, convenience, decency and morals”. The sole purpose of this chapter is to make that act punishable which pollute environment or threatens the life of the people. Section 268 classifies environmental crimes as a public nuisance and section 290 penalize the offence causing a public nuisance with a fine extending up to Rs. 200. Thus those who act or omit causing injury to others by environmental pollution, then they can be subject to prosecution. In *Murli S. Deora v. Union of India* (2001), the Supreme Court held that smoking in a public place is a violation of the fundamental right of those who don't smoke under article 21. Section 277 is applied for preventing water pollution and imposes imprisonment up to three months or fine up to Rs. 500 or both. The section uses terms such as public spring or reservoir whose interpretation by the courts has been quite restrictive as it does not include running water of rivers, streams, and canals. Again, under section 278, a fine up to Rs. 500 is imposed on any one who voluntarily spoils the surrounding by making it harmful for anyone health in general dwelling, or carrying a business in the neighborhood, or passing along the way of public. Apart from these, section 426, 430, 431 and 432 of IPC penalizes any pollution caused by mischief.

Similarly, Chapter X of the Criminal Procedure Code deals with the “maintenance of Public Order and Tranquility” and provides preventing and mitigating measures for public nuisance cases pertaining to soil, air, water and unsanitary conditions. Section 133 provides for the remedy to environmental pollution in general by empowering a District Magistrate and Sub Divisional Magistrate to stop the Nuisance.

There are certain other provisions primarily in two environmental legislations which are The Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1974, and Environment (Protection) Act 1986. Section 15 Of the Environment (Protection) Act 1986 provides that in case of contravention of rules, order direction of the Act, Provides for imprisonment of a maximum periods of five years maximum fine of one lakh rupees. If the contravention is continuing then an additional fine of a maximum of a five thousand rupees can be imposing every day. Furthermore, if the contravention exceeds beyond a period of one year after the date of conviction, the punishment can be extended to a maximum period of seven years. Again, section 47 of the Water Act makes a person vicariously liable for an offence committed by a company with that person being in charge of a business of the Company. An another is section 16 of the Environment Act which is *pari materia* to section 47 to Water Act.

Role of Police in prevention of Environmental Crime

Police is one of the basic components of Criminal Justice System in India. As an integral part of Criminal Justice Administration, Police have a vital role in the administration of criminal justice on environmental matters through detecting crimes, inspecting, investigating, violation, protecting business and tourist community policing. People are enshrined by the Constitution of India to live with human dignity and rights. Human life is precious and therefore everyone has the right to live with the freedoms given by our Constitution which are also subject to certain limitations as are determined by law. Police work encompasses preventive and protective roles in the course of maintaining law and order. Furthermore, prevention and promotion involve intimating programs to reduce environmental crime and educate citizens about the crime prevention measures.

International Criminal Police Organization, a network comprising 192 member nations, including India. Since 1992, INTERPOL’s work on environmental crimes is supported by INTERPOL’s Environmental Crime Working party, known as the Environmental Compliance and Enforcement Committee and its four specialized crime working groups on wildlife, forestry, fisheries and pollution crime. Each one of these working groups is comprised by senior law enforcement experts representing INTERPOL’s member country. Furthermore, they work in close collaboration with governmental, non-governmental and international organizations to disrupt transnational organized criminal groups involved in environmental crime. They offer investigative support to international cases and targets, coordinate operations, assist member countries to share information and conduct analysis into environmental criminal networks. Like any member nation, India maintains a National Crime Bureau which serve as the national platform for cooperation between domestic law enforcement units and the international police community. The NCB is the designated contact point for the NTERPOL. India has collaborated with the INTERPOL in talking a myriad of organized crime such as poaching, wildlife trafficking among others.

Moreover, the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change is the nodal agency in the administrative structure of the Central Government for the planning, promotion, coordination and overseeing the implementation of India's environmental and forestry policies and programs. The primary concern of the Ministry are implementation of policies and programs relating to conservations of the country's natural resources including its lakes and rivers, its biodiversity, forests and wildlife, ensuring the welfare of animals, and prevention and abatement of pollution. While implementing these policies and programmes, the Ministry is guided by the principle of sustainable development and enhancement of human well-being. The Green Police is the main enforcement and deterrence arm of the Ministry of Environmental Protection. The 2011 Enforcement Protection Law (Powers of Inspection and Protection) gives them the power to open cases, manage criminal investigations, impose fine and sanction etc. Green Police inspectors are involved with both monitoring and enforcing Environmental laws, regulations and decrees. Green Police enforce environmental laws on three levels: National, Regional and Local. At National level the Green Police take part in setting Ministry of Environmental Policy (MoEP), writing national legislation and regulations. They also conduct national enforcement operation to deal with environmental violation. At Regional level the Green Police work with the MoEP's district offices to maintain environmental Protection. Likewise, at Local level Green Police officers and inspectors work with local agencies and entities and local authority in order to enforce environmental laws. Furthermore, Green Police inspections are conducted on an ongoing basis, as well as within the framework of specific, planned operations. Investigations are done as a result of inspector own initiative or at the request of an MoEP department or district office after an environmental violation is discovered. In 2015, on the World Environment Day, India's first green police station was inaugurated at Maurice Nagar in north Delhi.

Conclusion

The UN Environment study identified several major gaps in the response to environmental crime. Lack of data, knowledge and awareness, lack of limited use of legislation, lack of institutional will and governance, lack of capacity of the enforcement chain, lack of international and national cooperation and information sharing among authorities and lack of engagement with private actors and local communities were among those. Some observer argues that the military and police have lack sufficient environment knowledge, therefore, their role should be restricted to supporting other actors with expertise such as environmental monitors and regulator. People should be empowered through education and make them aware about environmental rights and liabilities

In India, in order to prevent environmental crime a host of legislation existed but many of them are outmoded and irrelevant. The National Green Tribunal Act, 2010 does not provide a complete relief. It only deals with civil remedies not with criminal liability. The major gap that the Indian environmental law suffers from lack of the consideration those environmental crimes are serious. Such crimes are even lowly graded in the law enforcement priority list. Further, effective enforcement is lacking in respect of laws relevant to contemporary concerns and conducive to governance. This calls for a thorough review of laws, elimination of those which are outmoded and simplification of the procedures for implementing those

which is relevant. Internal reviews as well as learning's from international experience should be the basis of identifying filling gaps in existing laws. It must, however be recognized that laws in themselves do not provide solutions, unless there are mechanism to effectively enforce them. Appropriate mechanism for integrating them need to be created. Environmental crime is a growing concern and awareness and public participation is required to crime control and prevention.

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